

References

1. F. G. R. GIMBLETT, 'Inorganic Polymer Chemistry' Butterworths, London, 1963, P. 8, 405.
2. O. W. GIBBS, *Proc. Amer. Acad.*, 1885, 21, 105; *Amer. Chem. J.*, 1885, 7, 313, 392.
3. J. F. KEGGIN, *Proc., Royl. Soc.*, London, 1934, A144, 75.
4. S. K. ROY, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1976, 14A, 694.
5. J. A. LYONS and W. F. WILSON, *J. Polymer Sci.*, 1955, 87, 141.
6. S. F. WEST and L. F. ANDRIETH, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1955, 59, 1069.
7. A. A. BABAD-ZAKHRYAPIN, *Ah. neorg. Khim.*, 1959, 1, 445, 2403.
8. R. C. RAY and P. C. SINHA, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1946, 44, 790.

Mahanimbine and Murrayazoline from *Murraya exotica* Linn.* (Syn. *Murraya paniculata*)

P. BHATTACHARYYA, S. ROY, A. BISWAS, L. BHATTACHARYYA
and
D. P. CHAKRABORTY

Bose Research Institute, Calcutta 700 009

Manuscript received 21 May 1977, accepted 3 October 1977

ON chemotaxonomic considerations, we were interested to examine different species of the genus *Murraya* as one of the species *Murraya koenigii* Spreng. is the richest source of carbazole alkaloid¹. *Murraya exotica* has been the subject of numerous investigations² but so far no carbazole alkaloid has been reported from it. We, now report two carbazole alkaloids, mahanimbine, C₂₅H₂₅NO(I), m.p. 94° and murrayazoline C₂₅H₂₅NO(II), m.p. 260° from it.

The neutral fraction of the petroleum ether extract of the stem bark of *Murraya exotica* gave in a very poor yield a crystalline carbazole derivative m.p. 94°. The IR spectrum of the compound (I) showed the presence of -NH and an aromatic system. ($\nu_{\max}^{\text{Nujol}}$ 3359, 1647, 1613, 1575, 1493 cm⁻¹). The UV spectrum of (I) ($\nu_{\max}^{\text{EtOH}}$ 223, 239, 188, 330, 343 nm with log ϵ 4.55, 4.06, 4.61, 3.90, 3.42) was superimposable with that of mahanimbine³. The compound was identified as mahanimbine by direct comparison (T.L.C. and m.m.p.).

*Part 39 in the Series of Chemical Taxonomy. Part 38. S. Roy, R. Guha and D.P. Chakraborty, *Chem. & Ind.* (in press)

From the petroleum ether extract of the powdered leaf of *Murraya exotica* a crystalline colorless neutral Hot-II nitrogenous homogenous compound, m.p. 260°, [α]_D was isolated. The IR spectrum of the compound (II) showed the presence of an aromatic system ($\nu_{\max}^{\text{Nujol}}$ 1627, 1590, 1480, 1375, 1368, 852, 873 cm⁻¹). The UV spectrum ($\nu_{\max}^{\text{EtOH}}$ 245, 307 nm with log ϵ 4.69, 4.16) was suggestive of the presence of 2-methoxy carbazole chromophore. The physical and analytical data were suggestive of the identity of the compound with murrayazoline which was confirmed by the direct comparison with pure specimen of murrayazoline⁴ (mmp., TLC and UV, IR).

Though the yield of the two compounds are very poor, their occurrence in both the species (*M. exotica* and *M. koenigii*) is taxonomically interesting.

Acknowledgement

The authors thank Prof. S. K. Mukherjee, Director and Professor A. Sen, Head of the Department of Chemistry for their interest in the work.

References

1. D. P. CHAKRABORTY, *Fortschritte d. Chem. Org. Naturl.*, 1977, 34, 299.
2. K. RAJ, S. C. MISHRA, R. S. KAPIL and S. P. POPLI, *Phytochemistry*, 1976, 15, 1787 and references therein.
3. D. P. CHAKRABORTY, D. CHATTERJEE and S.N. GANGULY, *Chem. and Ind.*, 1969, 1662.
4. J. BORDNER, D. P. CHAKRABORTY, B. K. CHOWDHURY, S.N. GANGULY, K.C. DAS and B. WEINSTEIN, *Experientia*, 1972, 28, 1406.

Chemical Constituents of *Pteris longifolia*

(MISS) MANJU SEN AND (MISS) USHA SARKAR

Department of Chemistry, University of Kalyani, Kalyani, Nadia, West Bengal

Manuscript received 24 May 1977, accepted 3 October 1977

EARLIER communications^{1,2} from this laboratory reported the isolation and characterisation of wallichoside, β -sitosteryl palmitate, β -sitosterol, Pterosin B and Pterosin C from the alcoholic and benzene extract of the rhizomes of an Indian fern, *Pteris wallichiana* (Pteridaceae) respectively. The present report deals with a thorough and systematic chemical investigations of the benzene extract of the whole plant of *Pteris longifolia* (Pteridaceae) as no phytochemical investigations on this fern have so far been reported. This fern and *Pteris biurata*³ are the only two exceptions in this family so far

reported which did not afford any pteroin or its derivatives.

The air-dried powdered *P. longifolia* was extracted with hot benzene for 18 hrs. The benzene extract was separated into ether soluble and ether insoluble fractions. The latter fraction on column chromatography over silica gel followed by crystallisation from petether-acetone yield a solid, m. p. 88-90°, which was found to be the n tricontanyl ester of hexacosanic acid. $\nu_{\max}^{\text{K.Br}}$ 1730, 1170, 730 and 720 cm^{-1} . *MS* m/e 816 (M^+), 420 (M^+ —hexacosanic acid, $\text{C}_{26}\text{H}_{52}\text{O}_2$), 396. On hydrolysis with methanolic alkali (5%) gave n-triacontanol⁴ $\text{C}_{30}\text{H}_{62}\text{O}$, m.p. 90-91°. $\nu_{\max}^{\text{nujol}}$ 3210, 730 and 720 cm^{-1} . *MS* m/e 420 (M^+ — H_2O), 392 (M^+ — C_2H_4 — H_2O), 364 (M^+ — H_2O — $2 \times \text{C}_2\text{H}_4$) suggesting it to be an alcohol⁵ having more than four carbon atoms. (Found: C, 82.2; H, 13.9; $\text{C}_{30}\text{H}_{62}\text{O}$ requires C, 82.11; H, 14.24%) and hexacosanic acid⁶, $\text{C}_{26}\text{H}_{52}\text{O}_2$, m.p. 78-82°, $\nu_{\max}^{\text{nujol}}$ 1700, 730 and 720 cm^{-1} . *MS* m/e 396 M^+ , 368 (M^+ —28).

The ether soluble fraction was separated into acidic and neutral fractions. The acidic fraction on chromatographic separation followed by crystallisation gave palmitic acid⁷, $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{32}\text{O}_2$, m.p. 70-71°. $\nu_{\max}^{\text{nujol}}$ 700, and 730 and 720 cm^{-1} . *MS* m/e 256 (M^+), 185, 129, 73, 60.

The neutral fraction was chromatographed over a column of silica gel. Elution with a mixture of petether-benzene (4 : 1) yielded a gummy solid which on crystallisation from chloroform-acetone furnished crystalline β -sitosteryl palmitate⁸, $\text{C}_{45}\text{H}_{80}\text{O}_2$, m.p. 85-86°. $\nu_{\max}^{\text{nujol}}$ 1730, 1165, 720 cm^{-1} . *MS* m/e 396 (M^+ —palmitic acid), 382, 367, 288, 275, 255, 213, identical (m.m.p. and I.R.) with an authentic specimen. On hydrolysis this ester yielded β -sitosterol⁹, m.p. 136-138°, acetate, m.p. 126-128°, and a fatty acid which was identified (m.m.p. and I.R.) as palmitic acid, $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{32}\text{O}_2$, m.p. 65-70°. Elution of the column with petrolbenzene (3 : 2) afforded a

petether benzene solid which on crystallisation from chloroform-methanol furnished β -sitosteryl acetate $\text{C}_{31}\text{H}_{52}\text{O}_2$, m.p. 126-128°, identical (m.m.p. and I.R.) with an authentic sample. Further elution of the column with petether-benzene m.p., (2 : 3) gave β -sitosterol, m.p.p. 136-138°, acetate, m.p. 126-128°, identical with an authentic specimen.

Acknowledgement

The authors are highly indebted to Prof. P. Sengupta, Head, Department of Chemistry, University of Kalyani, for his guidance and encouragement, Dr. S. C. Pakrashi, Assistant Director, Indian Institute of Experimental Medicine, Calcutta, for spectral measurements and University Grant Commission, New Delhi for financial assistance to one of them (U. S.)

References

1. P. SENGUPTA, M. SEN, S.K. NIYOGI, S. C. PAKRASHI, and ALI, E., *Phytochem.*, 1976, 15/6, 995.
2. P. SENGUPTA, M. SEN, M. BASAK, S. C. PAKRASHI, and ALI, E., *Indian J. Chem.*, 1976, 817.
3. S. N. BOSE, and H. N. KHASTGIR, *Indian J. Appl. Chem.*, 1969, 401.
4. I. HEILBRON, H. M. BUNBURY, A. H. COOK, and E. R. H. JONES, 'Dictionary of Organic Compounds,' Eyre and Spottiswoode, London, 1953, Vol. IV, p. 538.
5. H. BUDZIKIEWICZ, C. DJERASSI, and H. WILLIAMS, 'Mass Spectrometry of Organic Compounds', Holden-Day, Inc. London, 1967, p. 99.
6. I. HEILBRON, H. M. CUNBURY, A. H. COOK, and E. R. H. JONES, 'Dictionary of Organic Compounds,' Eyre and Spottiswoode, London 1953, Vol. II, p. 99.
7. I. HEILBRON, H. M. BUNBURY, A. H. COOK, and E. R. H. JONES, 'Dictionary of Organic Compounds.' Eyre and Spottiswoode, London, 1953, Vol. II, p. 35.
8. Radt, F. Elsevier's Encyclopaedia of Organic Chemistry, Elsevier Publishing Company, New York, 1954, Vol. 14, p. 1817S.
9. I. HEILBRON, H. M. BUNBURY, A. H. COOK, and E. R. H. JONES, 'Dictionary of Organic Compounds', Eyre and Spottiswoode, London 1953, Vol. II, p. 361.